

The Influence of Live Streaming, Store Badge, and Store Rating on Brand Image and Purchasing Decisions at Treera Indonesia Stores in the Shopee Platform

Ricky Ramadhan¹, Abdul Halik², Estik Hari Prastiwi³

^{1,2,3}Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Surabaya

ABSTRACT: With the advancement of technology and the increasing penetration of the internet, consumer behavior has undergone significant changes. According to data from Analytic Data Advertising, there has been a dramatic surge of 400% in e-commerce activities since March 2020, which correlates with the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. This research aims to analyze the influence of live streaming, store badges, and store ratings on brand image and purchasing decisions, particularly in the context of online shopping, where consumer decisions are often based on digital information and virtual interactions. The population in this study consists of consumers of Treera Indonesia store. One hundred respondents were identified using purposive sampling techniques with criteria for high shopping intensity on the Shopee platform. Hypothesis testing in this research is conducted using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) based on Partial Least Square (PLS) approach. Based on the analysis of 7 hypotheses, it was found that 6 hypotheses were accepted, and 1 hypothesis was rejected. From these findings, it is concluded that live streaming, store badge, store ratings and brand image has a significant positive influence on purchasing decisions. Additionally, store badges and store ratings have a significant positive influence on brand image. However, live streaming does not have a significant influence on brand image.

KEYWORDS: live streaming, badge, rating, brand image, purchase decision

I. INTRODUCTION

Along with technological advances and increasing internet penetration, consumer behavior has experienced significant changes. Based on data from Analytic Data Advertising (ADA), there was a dramatic 400% spike in e-commerce activity starting from March 2020, which is in line with the start of the COVID-19 pandemic. Meanwhile, Bank Indonesia (BI) also reported that the number of transactions via online shopping platforms in March 2020 reached around 98.3 million, showing an increase of 18.1% compared to February of the same year.

This phenomenon not only shows changes in consumer behavior but also opens up huge opportunities for e-commerce platforms, such as Shopee. With more and more Indonesians choosing to shop online, the level of competition between various players in the e-commerce industry is increasing, especially in efforts to target certain market segments. This trend shows that the pandemic has accelerated the adoption of online shopping in Indonesia, and this has had a significant impact on the business strategies of e-commerce industry players. Additionally, this surge in activity is also driving innovation and service improvements in the sector, including the need to focus on brand image and purchasing decisions.

Live streaming, as one of the innovations in digital marketing, has received special attention in recent years. Live streaming, with its ability to present content in real-time and facilitate direct interactions between brands and consumers, provides an opportunity for brands to build closer, more authentic relationships with their audiences. Store badges and store ratings are also two important elements in e-commerce. Store badges, which are often awarded by e-commerce platforms as a form of recognition of a store's achievements or credibility, can increase consumer trust and demonstrate that the store has met certain standards. Meanwhile, store ratings, which are a reflection of consumer feedback and ratings, provide insight for other consumers regarding the quality of the products and services offered by the store.

II. THEORETICAL STUDY

A. Marketing Management

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2018; 34), marketing management is an effort made to create profitable exchanges and build strong relationships with consumers. Meanwhile, Lupiyoadi (2016:27) argues that marketing management involves analysis, planning, implementation and control of programs designed to create desired exchanges with target consumers, both for individual and collective benefit.

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B. Theory of Planned Behavior

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) which is a development of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) (Ajzen in Jogiyanto, 2007). Jogiyanto (2007) Developed this theory by adding constructs that were not yet in TRA. This construct is called perceived behavioral control. This construct was added to the TPB to control individual behavior which is limited by its shortcomings and the limitations of the lack of resources used to carry out its behavior (Hsu and Chiu 2002).

C. Live Streaming

Live streaming is a form of online interactive multimedia entertainment that is rapidly gaining popularity worldwide (Hilvert-Bruce et al., 2018). It is effective and easy to use, many people use live streaming for entertainment, communication or even promoting products and services. M. Zhang (2019) explains that Live streaming marketing is a broadcast online or in real time which enables business to business (B to B) or business to consumer (B to C) communications.

D. Store badge

A store badge in the context of e-commerce is a strategic element that functions as more than just a digital label or symbol on an online store profile page. This is a form of recognition or certification from the e-commerce platform that shows various positive aspects of the store, ranging from reliability, product quality, level of customer service, to the length of time the store has been operating. In some cases, this badge can also indicate the specialization of products or services offered by the store. The main function of store badges is to build trust and credibility, two elements that are very important in the online world where physical interaction between buyers and sellers is very limited. Consumers tend to have more trust in stores that have badges because they are deemed to have met the quality and reliability standards set by the e-commerce platform.

E. Store Rating

According to Ahmadi (2018: 4) Rating can be interpreted as a user's assessment of a product's preferences regarding their psychological and emotional experience that they undergo after interacting with a virtual product in a media environment. Ranking or rating products online is one way for consumers to think about the quality of online products, although sometimes things can happen in the measurement. This is mainly due to product assessments by consumers which reflect global consumer satisfaction, not only with the product, but also with how consumers are served by the online seller. According to Farki et al., (2016:2), rating can be interpreted as an assessment of the user's preference for a product regarding their experience referring to the psychological and emotional state they experience when interacting with a virtual product in a mediated environment.

F. Brand Image

Keller (2000) states that Brand Image is the consumer's perception of the product that will be consumed or used. Ferinda Dewi (2009) believes that brand image is a concept created by consumers for subjective reasons and personal emotions. According to Kotler and Keller (2009), brand image is the process by which someone selects, organizes, and interprets information input to create a meaningful image. According to Marhaeni Eka Saputri (2014), brand image is a perception that lasts a long time, is formed through experience, and is relatively consistent. Therefore, consumer attitudes and actions towards a brand image are one of the important elements that encourage consumers to buy a product.

G. Purchase Decision

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2019) purchasing decisions are decisions obtained by buyers in determining whether they want to buy a product through the process of deciding whether they want to make a transaction or not. According to Putri and Iriani (Rahmadayanti et al, 2022) Purchase decisions on E-commerce is a series of activities in evaluating several options and making purchasing decisions that are oriented towards purchasing based on facts referring to consumers in purchasing goods and services.

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III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure. 1 Conceptual Framework

Regarding the research context, problem formulation, literature review, and conceptual framework, then hypothesis that can be formed is as follows:

- H1: Live streaming has a significant effect on Purchase decisions at Treera Indonesia in Platform Shopee.
- H2: Badge Stores have a significant influence on Purchase decisions at Treera Indonesia in Platform Shopee.
- H3: Store rating has a significant effect on Purchase decisions at Treera Indonesia in Platform Shopee.
- H4: Live Streaming has a significant effect on the Brand Image at Treera Indonesia in Platform Shopee.
- H5: Badge Stores have a significant influence on the Brand Image at Treera Indonesia in Platform Shopee.
- H6: Store rating has a significant effect on the Brand Image at Treera Indonesia in Platform Shopee.
- H7: Brand Image has a significant influence on Purchase Decisions at Treera Indonesia in Platform Shopee.

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

A. Data Types and Sources

The approach taken is quantitative research, which aims to verify the hypothesis that has been determined by the researcher. The research method applied in this study is a survey in the form of a questionnaire. This research used primary data which were retrieved from November to December 2023.

B. Population

The population in this study are subjects related to the research the author conducted in marketplace Shopee, the respondents of this research are consumers of Treera Indonesia stores. Because the population of consumers at Treera Indonesia stores is unknown, the formula needed in the research to determine the sample size is to use the Lemeshow formula (Hening, 2015):

$$n = \frac{z^2 p (1 - p)}{d^2} = \frac{1.96^2 \cdot 0.5 (1 - 0.5)}{0.1^2} = \frac{0.9604}{0.01} = 96.04$$

Information:

n = Number of samples

p = Maximum estimate = 50% = 0.5

z = Standard Value = 1.96

d = alpha (0,10)/ sampling error = 10%

C. Data Collection

The data source used in this research is primary data, namely information obtained directly from the original source. Primary data is information provided directly by the source to the person collecting the data (Sugiyono, 2017:193). Information for this study was taken from a questionnaire distributed to Shopee users at Treera Indonesia stores, with a focus on the influence of live streaming, badge shop, and rating store on brand image and purchasing decisions. After collecting and recording data, researchers carried out

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interaction analysis consisting of data reduction, data presentation and verification. The analysis of this research takes place along with the data collection process, or is carried out after the data has been collected.

D. Data Analysis Method

Hypothesis testing in this research was carried out using an approach Structural Equation Model (SEM) based Partial Least Square (PLS). PLS is a component or variant-based structural equation model (SEM). Hypothesis testing is carried out to determine whether there is an effect of research variables on the others. This testing is done by analyzing the Regression Weight, i.e. Critical Ratio (CR) and Probability (P) values. The required limits are ≥ 1.96 for the CR value and ≤ 0.05 for the P-value. If the data processing results show a value that meets these requirements, the proposed research hypothesis is accepted.

V. RESULT & DISCUSSION

A. Evaluation of Measurement Model/ Outer Model

Figure. 2 Outer Model

To test convergent validity, Outer Loading and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) are utilized. An indicator is considered to meet convergent validity in the good category if the Outer Loading > 0.7 and the Average Variance Extracted > 0.5 . The following are the Outer Loading and Average Variance Extracted for each indicator in this research variable:

Table. 1 Convergent Validity Test - Outer Loading

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading
Live Streaming (X1)	X1.5	0,717
	X1.6	0,815
	X1.7	0,755
	X1.8	0,789
Store Badge (X2)	X2.4	0,847
	X2.5	0,820
	X2.7	0,837
	X2.8	0,789
Store Rating (X3)	X3.1	0,807
	X3.2	0,705
	X3.3	0,869
	X3.4	0,770
	X3.6	0,704
	X3.7	0,829
	X3.9	0,829

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Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading
Brand Image (Z)	X3.9	0,819
	Z.1	0,717
	Z.2	0,772
	Z.3	0,786
	Z.4	0,866
	Z.5	0,849
Purchase Decision (Y)	Z.6	0,734
	Y.3	0,767
	Y.4	0,765
	Y.6	0,811
	Y.8	0,774
	Y.9	0,820

Source: Data processed by *Smart-PLS*

Based on the data presented in Table 1 Outer Loading above, showing that there are no indicator variables with outer loading values below 0.5, thus all indicators are considered suitable or valid for use in the study and can be used for further analysis.

Table. 2 Convergent Validity Test - Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Live Streaming (X1)	0,593
Store Badge (X2)	0,678
Store Rating (X3)	0,621
Brand Image (Z)	0,623
Purchase Decision (Y)	0,620

Source: Data processed by *Smart-PLS*

Based on the data presented in Table 2, it is known that the Average Variance Extracted values for all variables in this study are > 0.5. Therefore, it can be stated that each variable has good convergent validity. In the next section, the results of discriminant validity testing will be explained using Fornell-Larcker and Cross Loading values. An indicator is considered to meet discriminant validity standards if the Fornell-Larcker and Cross Loading values for the indicator on its variable are the highest compared to other variables. The following are the Fornell-Larcker and Cross Loading values for each indicator:

Table. 3 Discriminant Validity Test - Fornell-Larcker

	X1	X2	X3	Z	Y
Live Streaming (X1)	0.770				
Store Badge (X2)	0.661	0.824			
Store Rating (X3)	0.433	0.544	0.788		
Brand Image (Z)	0.486	0.668	0.706	0.789	
Purchase Decision (Y)	0.546	0.663	0.697	0.726	0.788

Source: Data processed by *Smart-PLS*

Table. 4 Discriminant Validity Test - Cross Loading

	Live Streaming	Store Badge	Store Rating	Brand Image	Purchase Decision
X1.5	0,717	0,690	0,295	0,448	0,366
X1.6	0,815	0,614	0,465	0,387	0,480
X1.7	0,755	0,319	0,278	0,351	0,399
X1.8	0,789	0,379	0,275	0,303	0,432
X2.4	0,652	0,847	0,479	0,557	0,515
X2.5	0,498	0,820	0,444	0,537	0,518
X2.7	0,484	0,837	0,351	0,568	0,518
X2.8	0,540	0,789	0,513	0,536	0,625
X3.1	0,374	0,400	0,807	0,620	0,535
X3.2	0,276	0,256	0,705	0,492	0,368
X3.3	0,446	0,450	0,869	0,644	0,578
X3.4	0,524	0,514	0,770	0,720	0,610
X3.6	0,254	0,491	0,704	0,719	0,563

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	Live Streaming	Store Badge	Store Rating	Brand Image	Purchase Decision
X3.7	0,226	0,449	0,829	0,651	0,557
X3.9	0,249	0,376	0,819	0,536	0,578
Z1.1	0,155	0,380	0,616	0,717	0,384
Z1.2	0,281	0,492	0,481	0,772	0,572
Z1.3	0,321	0,571	0,471	0,786	0,587
Z1.4	0,464	0,618	0,821	0,866	0,532
Z1.5	0,486	0,584	0,701	0,849	0,650
Z1.6	0,508	0,486	0,674	0,734	0,677
Y3	0,534	0,652	0,631	0,659	0,767
Y4	0,387	0,424	0,425	0,501	0,765
Y6	0,389	0,486	0,501	0,581	0,811
Y8	0,473	0,494	0,551	0,560	0,774
Y9	0,334	0,509	0,596	0,528	0,820

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data presented in Tables 3 and 4, it can be observed that each indicator on the research variable has the highest Fornell-Larcker and Cross Loading values on the variable it forms compared to the Fornell-Larcker and Cross Loading values on other variables. Based on these results, it can be stated that the indicators used in this study have good discriminant validity in constructing their respective variables.

This section presents the results of reliability testing using composite reliability, rho_A, and Cronbach's alpha values. An indicator is considered to meet reliability standards if the composite reliability values are > 0.6 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1998; Chin & Dibbern, 2010), and the rho_A and Cronbach's alpha values are > 0.7 (Vinzi, Trinchera, & Amato, 2010). The following are the values of composite reliability, rho_A, and Cronbach's alpha for each indicator:

Table. 5 Reliability Test - Composite Reliability, rho_A, and Cronbach's Alpha

Variable	Composite Reliability	rho_A	Cronbach's Alpha
Live Streaming (X1)	0,771	0,773	0,853
Store Badge (X2)	0,842	0,842	0,894
Store Rating (X3)	0,771	0,773	0,853
Brand Image (Z)	0,878	0,887	0,908
Purchase Decision (Y)	0,848	0,853	0,891

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data presented in Table 5 above, it can be observed that the composite reliability values for all research variables are > 0.6 , and the values for rho_A and Cronbach's alpha are > 0.7 . These results indicate that each variable has met the criteria for composite reliability, rho_A, and Cronbach's alpha. Therefore, it can be concluded that the overall variables have a high level of reliability.

B. Evaluation of Structural Model/ Inner Model

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Figure. 3 Inner Model

Based on the inner model scheme presented in Figure 3, it can be explained that the largest path coefficient is indicated by the influence of Store Rating on Brand Image, that the coefficient equals to 28.396, followed by the influence of Store badge on Brand Image, equal to 10.420. Meanwhile, the smallest influence is shown by Live Streaming on Brand Image, equals to 0.066. Based on these descriptions, it is evident that all variables in this model have positive path coefficients. This indicates that the larger the value of the path coefficient for an exogenous variable on an endogenous variable, the stronger its influence.

Table. 6 R-Square

	R-Square
Brand Image	0.724
Purchase Decision	0.629

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data in table 6 above, it can be seen that the R-Square values for the Store Rating and Purchase Decision variables are 0.724 and 0.629 respectively, which means the ability of the exogenous variable to explain the endogenous variable is 72.4% (strong) and 62.9% (moderate) where 27.6% and the remaining 37.1% are the influence of other exogenous variables not measured in this study.

Table. 7 Path Coefficient

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T-Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Signification
Live Streaming (X1) → Purchase Decision (Y)	0,132	0,125	0,050	2,619	0,009	Significant positive
Store Badge (X2) → Purchase Decision (Y)	0,238	0,244	0,050	4,739	0,000	Significant positive
Store Rating (X3) → Purchase Decision (Y)	0,299	0,302	0,047	6,359	0,000	Significant positive
Live Streaming (X1) → Brand Image (Z)	-0,002	0,000	0,027	0,066	0,948	Not significant
Store Badge (X2) → Brand Image (Z)	0,327	0,325	0,031	10,420	0,000	Significant positive

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T-Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Signification
Store Rating (X3) → Brand Image (Z)	0,629	0,629	0,022	28,396	0,000	Significant positive
Brand Image (Z) → Purchase Decision (Y)	0,262	0,260	0,041	6,352	0,000	Significant positive

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Table 7 shows the results of the PLS calculation which states the influence between variables. Based on the table above, it can be seen that of the 7 hypotheses processed in this research, it can be declared accepted or significant if the P-Values < 0.05 and T-statistics > 1.96. There is 1 hypothesis which states that the effect is not significant while 6 other hypotheses state that it has a significant positive.

H1: Live Streaming influences Purchase Decision

Based on the results of statistical tests that have been carried out, it was found that the influence of live streaming on purchasing decisions shows that the Original Sample (O) results are 0.132, indicating that these two variables have a positive influence, with a P-Values of 0.009 which meets the P-Values standard < 0.05, so it can be concluded that the first hypothesis in this study was accepted and significant.

These results indicate that the use of live streaming as a marketing tool has a strong positive impact in encouraging consumers to make purchases. This happens because live streaming increases engagement and interaction between brands and consumers, enables real-time product demonstrations, and builds trust through transparency and interactivity. By displaying products in a live setting, consumers gain a better understanding of the product's quality and applications, which reduces uncertainty in online purchases.

Live streaming allows personalization of content to suit the target audience, increasing product relevance and appeal. The viral potential of live streaming sessions can expand a brand's reach and increase brand awareness significantly. The opportunity to get direct feedback from consumers is also a plus, allowing Treera to adjust their product and marketing strategies more effectively. Overall, live streaming is an invaluable tool for Treera in influencing consumer purchasing decisions, especially in the competitive fashion accessories market.

These results are in line with research conducted by Amin, D.E.R., et al (2023) and Dirnaeni, D., et al (2021) which said that live streaming has a significant positive effect on purchasing decisions. Meanwhile, these results are not in line with research conducted by Lestari, S.R.I (2021) and Agustin, N.A (2023) who said that live streaming insignificant effect on purchasing decisions.

H2: Store Badge influences Purchase Decision

Based on the results of statistical tests that have been carried out, it was found that the influence of store badges on purchasing decisions shows that the Original Sample (O) results are 0.238, stating that these two variables have a positive influence, with a P-Values of 0.000, it meets the P-Values standard < 0.05, so it can be concluded that the second hypothesis in this study was accepted and significant.

These results show that the presence of a badge or recognition as a trusted shop on e-commerce platforms such as Shopee plays an important role in influencing consumer purchasing decisions. In the context of Treera Indonesia, this means that when their shop gets a badge, such as Top Seller or Verified Seller, this significantly increases consumer trust in the brand. The badge acts as a symbol of reliability and credibility, giving consumers a sense of security when making a purchase, especially important in an online environment where physical interaction with the product is impossible.

This trust is very crucial in the world of unisex fashion accessories, where product quality and authenticity are the main considerations. Additionally, the badge can differentiate Treera from other competitors, giving them a competitive edge. Consumers tend to feel more comfortable buying from stores that have received official recognition from e-commerce platforms, thereby increasing the likelihood of purchase. Therefore, obtaining and maintaining store badges is an important strategy for Treera Indonesia to improve purchasing decisions and strengthen their position in the market.

These results are in line with research conducted by Hariyanto, H.T., et al (2021) and Suriyanto, A.D (2017) who said that store badges have a significant influence on purchasing decisions. Meanwhile, these results are not in line with research conducted by Ningsih, C.K (2023) which said that store badges had no significant effect on purchasing decisions.

H3: Store Rating influences Purchase Decision

Based on the results of statistical tests that have been carried out, it was found that the influence of store ratings on purchasing decisions shows that the Original Sample (O) results are 0.229, indicating that these two variables have a positive influence, with a P-Values of 0.000 meeting the P-Values standard < 0.05, so it can be concluded that the third hypothesis in this research is accepted and significant.

These results confirm that high and positive ratings for stores on e-commerce platforms such as Shopee play a crucial role in guiding consumer purchasing decisions. For Treera Indonesia, this means that good reviews and ratings from consumers not only improve

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the store's reputation but also directly influence buyers' trust and readiness to make transactions. High store ratings are often considered an indicator of previous customer satisfaction and product quality, two important factors in purchasing decisions, especially in the fashion accessories industry where quality and authenticity are critical.

In an online environment, where consumers cannot touch or feel a product before purchasing, positive ratings from other buyers become an invaluable assessment tool. This provides powerful social confirmation, increasing trust in the brand and reducing hesitation when shopping. Therefore, for Treera Indonesia, ensuring a positive customer experience and encouraging them to leave good reviews is important, not only to maintain high ratings but also to improve future purchasing decisions.

These results are in line with research conducted by Hariyanto, H.T., et al (2021), Ardianti, A.N, et al (2019) and Hidayati, N.L (2018) who said that store ratings have a significant effect on purchasing decisions. Meanwhile, these results are not in line with research conducted by Ilmiyah, K, et al (2020) which said that store ratings had no significant effect on purchasing decisions.

H4: Live Streaming influences Brand Image

Based on the results of statistical tests that have been carried out, it was found that the influence of live streaming on brand image shows that the Original Sample (O) results are -0.002, indicating that these two variables have a negative influence, with a P-Values of 0.948 which does not meet the P-Values standard > 0.05 , so it can be concluded that the fourth hypothesis in this study is rejected and is not significant.

These results indicate that in the context of Treera Indonesia, live streaming activities may not have a significant impact on brand perception or image in the eyes of consumers. This could mean that while live streaming is effective in increasing engagement and likelihood of purchase, other factors such as content quality, frequency, and relevance of live streaming to the target audience may not be strong enough to build or change the overall brand image. This could also indicate that consumers may focus more on other aspects such as product quality, price, or reviews rather than live streaming content when forming their perception of a brand.

In Treera Indonesia's case, this could mean there needs to be an adjustment in the live streaming content strategy or a combination with other marketing initiatives to create a more significant impact on the brand image. There may also be other factors that are more influential in building a brand image in the unisex fashion accessories market that must be considered. Therefore, Treera needs to re-evaluate their approach to live streaming in their overall marketing strategy, perhaps by integrating it more closely with other branding and marketing elements.

The results of this study provide a significant contribution to the understanding of influence live streaming on brand image, filling knowledge gaps in existing literature. Because there has been no previous research that specifically discusses the influence between live streaming and brand image. Therefore, this finding can be considered as a novelty or update in the context of this research.

H5: Store Badge influences Brand Image

Based on the results of statistical tests that have been carried out, it was found that the influence of store badges on brand image shows that the Original Sample (O) results are 0.327, stating that these two variables have a positive influence, with a P-Values of 0.000, it meets the P-Values standard < 0.05 , so it can be It was concluded that the fifth hypothesis in this study was accepted and significant.

These results show that giving badges or official recognition to Treera Indonesia on e-commerce platforms such as Shopee has a significant impact in strengthening their brand image. This means that badges such as Top Seller or Verified Seller not only increase consumer trust but also effectively improve consumer perceptions of Treera's quality and reputation as a brand. In the fashion accessories industry, where trust and credibility are paramount, badges serve as an affirmation of quality and reliability, giving consumers a sense of security and confidence in the brand.

By earning a store badge, Treera not only increases its visibility among competitors but also builds a strong and trusted brand identity. This is especially important in the online shopping environment, where consumers often have to rely on visual and symbolic indicators to make purchasing decisions. Therefore, strategies for acquiring and maintaining store badges should be an important part of Treera's branding efforts, as they directly contribute to how consumers perceive and value their brand.

The results of this study provide a significant contribution to the understanding of influence store badge on brand image, filling knowledge gaps in existing literature. Because there has been no previous research that specifically discusses the influence between store badge and brand image. Therefore, this finding can be considered as a novelty or update in the context of this research.

H6: Store Rating influences Brand Image

Based on the results of the statistical tests that have been carried out, it was found that the effect of store rating on brand image shows that the Original Sample (O) results are 0.629, indicating that these two variables have a positive influence, with a P-Values of 0.000 which meets the P-Values standard < 0.05 , so it can be It was concluded that the sixth hypothesis in this study was accepted and significant.

These results confirm that for Treera Indonesia, high store ratings on e-commerce platforms such as Shopee significantly contribute to the formation and strengthening of a positive brand image in the eyes of consumers. A good store rating, which reflects previous customer satisfaction, is a key indicator of the reliability and quality of the products offered. In the unisex fashion accessories

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industry, where product perception is highly dependent on consumer trust in the brand, positive store ratings play a vital role in establishing a strong brand image. This shows that consumers are not only satisfied with their purchase, but also that their experience with Treera has met or exceeded expectations, which directly impacts how the brand is viewed by other potential consumers.

These positive ratings provide social confirmation and help build Treera's reputation as a reliable and quality brand, making it easier for new consumers to trust and choose Treera over competitors. Therefore, ensuring that customers have a positive experience and encouraging them to leave good reviews becomes crucial, not only for sales success but also for sustainable brand image building. The results of this study provide a significant contribution to the understanding of influence store rating on brand image, filling knowledge gaps in existing literature. Because there has been no previous research that specifically discusses the influence between store rating and brand image. Therefore, this finding can be considered as a novelty or update in the context of this research.

H7: Brand Image influences Purchase Decision

Based on the results of the statistical tests that have been carried out, it was found that the influence of brand image on purchasing decisions shows that the Original Sample (O) results are 0.262, indicating that these two variables have a positive influence, with a P-Values of 0.000 which meets the P-Values standard < 0.05 , so it can be concluded that the seventh hypothesis in this study was accepted and significant.

These results indicate that for Treera Indonesia, building and maintaining a positive brand image is the main key in influencing consumer purchasing decisions. A strong and positive brand image in the eyes of consumers creates a higher perceived value for the products offered. In the context of unisex fashion accessories, where consumer choices are often driven by brand identity and values, a positive brand image can increase product appeal and encourage consumer loyalty. A good brand image not only helps in differentiating Treera Indonesia from its competitors but also helps in building emotional connections with consumers, which is an important factor in purchasing decisions.

This means that investing in marketing and branding activities that strengthen the brand image, such as advertising campaigns, collaborations with influencers, and consistency in quality and service, will pay dividends in the form of increased sales. Brand image serves as a guarantor of quality and authenticity, which is very important in influencing purchasing decisions, especially in online marketplaces where consumers cannot physically inspect products before purchasing.

Therefore, Treera must continue to focus on strategies that enhance and maintain their positive brand image to maximize success in the online marketplace. These results are in line with research conducted by Lestari, S.R.I (2021), Laily, N.M, et al (2023), Budianto, C, et al (2023), Azhari, A, et al (2023), and Cahya, A.D, et al (2023) which says that brand image has a significant influence on purchasing decisions.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this research, 100 Treera Indonesia shop consumers who made transactions via the Shopee platform were the main sample using the purposive sampling method. Data analysis shows the following results. First, live streaming is effective as a marketing tool with a strong positive impact in driving consumers, especially in the competitive fashion accessories market. Second, the presence of badges as a sign of recognition of trusted stores on e-commerce platforms positively influences consumer trust in the brand and increases the likelihood of purchase. Third, high and positive store ratings on e-commerce platforms play a crucial role in guiding consumer purchasing decisions, providing social confirmation, and increasing trust in the brand. Although live streaming is effective in increasing engagement and likelihood of purchase, its impact on brand perception or image in the eyes of consumers is considered insignificant. Therefore, Treera needs to re-evaluate their approach to live streaming in marketing strategy. Fifth, badges and high store ratings make a significant contribution to building and strengthening a positive brand image in the eyes of consumers. In conclusion, building and maintaining a positive brand image for Treera Indonesia has proven to be the main key in influencing consumer purchasing decisions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are suggestions from the author for further research based on our research results.

1. Live streaming has not been proven to have a significant influence on brand image, but the use of live streaming can be optimized to improve purchasing decisions. Treera Indonesia can consider a live streaming strategy that is more interactive, informative and interesting to attract customer attention.
2. The positive results of store badges and store ratings on purchasing decisions and brand image, Treera Indonesia is advised to continue to improve service quality, obtain positive feedback, and promote store badges more actively and maintain them.
3. Improving brand image can be achieved through stronger branding strategies and empowering elements that are proven to increase positive customer perceptions, such as store badges and store ratings.
4. With a deeper understanding, it is recommended to carry out further analysis regarding other factors that might influence purchasing decisions and brand image, as well as conducting further research to validate these findings in different time contexts.

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